

IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE PLATES SUBJECT TO HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT BY RIGID PROJECTILES: ANALYTICAL MODELLING OF THE ELASTIC RESPONSE.

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ABSTRACT

Analytical models are developed to predict the elastic dynamic response of circular clamped composite plates subject to high-velocity impact by a rigid projectile. The models are based on first-order shear deformation theory of plates and take into account the effects of large deformations, anisotropic behavior of the composite material, propagation of flexural waves and higher-order vibrational modes emerging in the boundary-controlled phase of response. The dynamic response was found to be governed by only four non-dimensional parameters: aspect ratio, mass ratio, non-dimensional impact velocity and transverse shear stiffness, respectively. The analytical models were validated by comparing their predictions to those obtained from detailed dynamic FE simulations and a good correlation was found for a wide range of parameters. Both analytical and FE predictions showed very small differences in the responses of cross-ply and a quasi-isotropic composites of equal areal mass, and their elastic deflection response was found to be only mildly sensitive to the projectile radius. In addition, the sensitivity of peak tensile strain to variations of impact velocity was examined for two types of composites, carbon-fiber/epoxy (CFRP) and glass-fiber/epoxy (GFRP) composites. It was shown that the critical velocities associated with the inception of failure were found below the measured limit velocities for full penetration, and the GFRP plates sustained higher impact velocities at the inception of failure compared to plates made from stiffer and more brittle CFRP of equal mass. Finally, the validated analytical models were used to construct design maps in order to aid selection of damage-resistant plate geometries.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber composites have made their entrance into a wide range of engineering applications because they combine low weight, high stiffness and strength as well as excellent corrosion resistance. For many industrial applications where composites are progressively being used, material damage and failure due to high-velocity impact by projectiles or fragments is a major concern. In the last decades, the dynamic response of composite laminates consequent to impact loading by hard projectiles has been extensively studied. In composite materials, energy absorption due to plastic deformation is very limited and their impact response leads to deformation modes dictated by propagation of longitudinal, shear and flexural waves travelling in the material at different velocities [1].

The impact resistance of a structure is often quantified by the limit velocity (or ballistic limit), defined as the velocity required for a projectile to penetrate a given material at least 50% of the time. When laminates are impacted at velocities below the ballistic limit, matrix cracking and delamination have been recognized to be the main energy dissipation mechanisms, as observed experimentally by

Takeda et al. [2] and Heimbs et al. [3]. Other authors [4, 5] employed theoretical modelling approaches to study delamination of laminates subject to transverse impact.

Studies investigating the deformation and failure mechanisms of laminates impacted above the ballistic limit are extensively described in the literature and a comprehensive review of existing work on this subject can be found in Abrate [6]. For example, Wen [7] derived a simple empirical relationship for the ballistic limit of fiber-reinforced composites, taking into account the nose shape of the projectile. Cantwell and Morton [8] observed the mechanisms of perforation of thin CFRP beams and noted that plate failure involved a shear-off penetration in the upper half of the plate (impact side) and tensile breakage of plies in the bottom half. While CFRP and GFRP laminates are the most widely used composite systems in engineering applications, the recent development of new fibers with extremely high stiffness to weight ratios has greatly improved the ballistic performance of composite laminates. They include Nylon, aramids (e.g. Kevlar®), ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (e.g. Spectra®, Dyneema®) and PBO (e.g. Zylon®). Detailed studies on the perforation resistance of the latter composite systems are extensively reported in the literature, see e.g. in Zhu et al. [9], Cunniff [10] and Karthikeyan et al. [11].

A considerable body of literature exists on numerical and theoretical predictions of the elastic response of composite plates subject to various dynamic loading conditions. A possible analytical treatment of impact on elastic plates involves expressing the transient plate response in terms of mode shapes and natural frequencies, as described in Zener [12], Olsson [13] and Sun and Chattopadhyay [14]. While this technique can be readily applied to simply supported plates, finite strain solutions for the impact behavior of elastic plates with fully-clamped boundaries are obtained in the published literature via approximate techniques, see e.g. Qian & Swanson [15] for the case of rectangular carbon/epoxy plates, Hoo Fatt and Palla [16] for the case of composite sandwich plates and Phoenix and Porwal [17] for elastic membrane impacted transversely by a cylindrical projectile. However, the models cited above are limited to the early phase of the response, dictated by propagation of flexural waves, and cannot be used to predict the boundary-controlled phase of response.

In this study we derive an analytical model for the dynamic response of a fully-clamped, circular composite plate subject to high velocity impact by a rigid projectile, taking into account the effect of higher order vibrational modes, activated upon reflection of flexural waves at the boundaries. Effects of transverse shear deformations, large deflections and flexural wave propagation will also be modelled. The model is based on a linear elastic material response but accounts for the geometric non-linearities in the problem and, to some extent, for material anisotropy. It is clear that the prediction of the ballistic limit of arbitrary composite plates is beyond the scope of the present study, which does not attempt modeling the complex damage mechanisms activated in composite laminates upon impact. On the other hand the model presented here provides, for a certain class of composite plates and for an arbitrary projectile, the critical impact velocity at the onset of tensile ply failure. The model allows identifying the four main governing non-dimensional groups of the impact problem and predicts two possible, regimes of behavior. Finally, design maps are constructed to aid the selection of materials and geometries for damage resistant composite plates.

2 ANALYTICAL MODELING

Consider a fully clamped circular plate of thickness h and radius R made from an orthotropic, elastic composite laminate of areal mass $\mu = \rho h$, as sketched in Fig. 1 (ρ denotes the average density of the laminate). The plate is subject to dynamic transverse loading by impact of a rigid spherical projectile of mass M and radius R_s , travelling at a velocity v_0 perpendicular to the plate surface (Fig. 1a). Here, attention is restricted to impact of relatively large projectiles, i.e. $2R_s > h$, on plates with small to moderate aspect ratios, $0.02 < h/R < 0.15$. For these ranges it is reasonable to assume that plate indentation is small compared to the transverse deflection w_0 of the plate centre and can therefore be neglected.

Following Schiffer and Tagarielli [18], we assume that the initial phase of response is dictated by propagation of a flexural wave, emanating from the impact point and propagating towards the boundary, see Fig. 1. Despite the dispersive behaviour of flexural waves [1], impact experiments on composite plates [11, 19] have shown that the shape of the dynamic disturbance does not appreciably

change during this phase and that the flexural wave front can be idealised by an elastic wave front propagating at a velocity $\dot{\zeta}$ in the positive r -direction, see Fig. 1b. To this end, we assume a simple axisymmetric polynomial displacement field to describe the initial deformation response of the composite plate, $w(r,t)$, in terms of two degrees of freedom: the centre deflection $w_0(t)$ and the flexural wave position $\zeta(t)$. When the flexural wave front reaches the boundary of the plate, i.e. $\zeta = R$ (see Fig. 1c), the plate deflection profile is affected by the boundary conditions. We denote as ‘Phase 1’ the response ranging from $t = 0$ to the instant, t_1 , when the flexural wave reaches the plate’s centre point, i.e. $\zeta(t_1) = R$, while ‘Phase 2’ represents the response at subsequent times.

Figure 1: Transient deformation of a clamped elastic plate subject to impact of a rigid projectile: (a) projectile impinges on the target, (b) propagation of a flexural wave.

2.1 Phase 1 response

To describe the plate’s response during Phase 1 we assume that the deflection within the portion $0 \leq r \leq \zeta(t)$ can be approximated by an axisymmetric polynomial shape function that satisfies the boundary conditions. Such a function may be written as

$$w(r,t) = w_0(t) \left[1 - \frac{3r^2}{\zeta(t)^2} + \frac{2r^3}{\zeta(t)^3} \right], \quad (1)$$

where $w_0(t)$ denotes the plate’s centre deflection and $\zeta(t)$ is the flexural wave position (Fig. 1b); for $r > \zeta(t)$, the plate is assumed to remain straight during Phase 1, hence $w(r,t) = 0$. Note that for transverse impact of plates, radial and tangential mid-plane displacements are typically vanishingly small compared to the transverse deflections, hence we assume $u = 0$ and $v = 0$ in the following analysis. A shear deformation profile that is compatible with the boundary conditions and symmetry requirements is given by

$$\gamma_{rz}(r,t) = \gamma_{rz0}(t) \sin \left(\frac{r\pi}{\zeta(t)} \right)^2, \quad (2)$$

with $\gamma_{rz0}(t)$ the shear deformation amplitude.

We describe the response of the composite by four effective elastic constants

$$E_r = \frac{1}{hA'_{11}}; \nu_{r\phi} = -\frac{A'_{12}}{A'_{11}}; E_{fr} = \frac{12}{h^3D'_{11}}; G_r = \frac{1}{hS'_{11}} \quad (3)$$

where E_r , $\nu_{r\phi}$, E_{fr} and G_r are the effective in-plane modulus, Poisson’s ratio, flexural modulus and transverse shear modulus, respectively, A'_{11} is the first element of the laminate’s in-plane compliance matrix, $\mathbf{A}' = \text{inv}(\mathbf{A})$, D'_{11} is the first element of the laminate’s bending compliance matrix, $\mathbf{D}' = \text{inv}(\mathbf{D})$, and S'_{11} is the first element of the laminate’s shear compliance matrix, $\mathbf{S}' = \text{inv}(\mathbf{S})$. It is important to mention that A'_{11} , A'_{12} , D'_{11} and S'_{11} in eq. (3) are, in general, dependent on the choice of reference system and vary along the circumferential direction ϕ . In order to obtain effective averages, the properties (3) were evaluated n times (typically $n = 8$) in different reference systems obtained by rotating an arbitrary cylindrical system about the z -axis by increments $\phi_j = 2\pi j/n$

($j = 0, 1, \dots, n$) and the corresponding properties E_r^j , G_r^j and $\nu_{r\phi}^j$ were averaged to obtain the effective laminate properties as

$$\tilde{E}_r = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=0}^n E_r^j ; \quad \tilde{\nu}_{r\phi} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=0}^n \nu_{r\phi}^j ; \quad \tilde{G}_r = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=0}^n G_r^j . \quad (4)$$

The response of the composite is isotropic in the plane of the plate but has bending and shear moduli independent of the in-plane properties. For the composites modelled in this work, the very small differences between E_{fr} and E_r allowed to assume $\tilde{E}_{fr} \approx \tilde{E}_r$.

We now use first-order shear deformation theory to write the kinematic relations for the plate

$$u(r, z, t) = z\theta_r(r, t) ; \quad w(r, z, t) = w(r, t) \quad (5)$$

where u and w are the displacements in the r and z directions, respectively, and θ_r denotes the rotation of the cross-section in the rz -plane, with reference to the coordinate system shown in Fig. 1. The von Karman strain-displacement relations can then be written as

$$\varepsilon_{rr} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w(r, t)}{\partial r} \right)^2 + z \frac{\partial \theta_r(r, t)}{\partial r} ; \quad \varepsilon_{\phi\phi} = \varepsilon_{r\phi} = \gamma_{r\phi} = 0 ; \quad \gamma_{rz} = \frac{\partial w(r, t)}{\partial r} + \theta_r(r, t), \quad (6)$$

and the corresponding curvatures of the middle-surface are

$$\kappa_{rr} = \frac{\partial \theta_r}{\partial r} ; \quad \kappa_{\phi\phi} = \frac{1}{r} \theta_r ; \quad \kappa_{r\phi} = 0. \quad (7)$$

Now write the in-plane forces, bending moments and shear forces

$$\begin{aligned} N_{rr} &= C(\varepsilon_{rr} + \tilde{\nu}_{r\phi} \varepsilon_{\phi\phi}) ; \quad N_{\phi\phi} = C\tilde{\nu}_{r\phi} \varepsilon_{rr} ; \quad N_{r\phi} = 0 ; \\ M_{rr} &= -D(\kappa_{rr} + \tilde{\nu}_{r\phi} \kappa_{\phi\phi}) ; \quad M_{\phi\phi} = -D(\kappa_{\phi\phi} + \tilde{\nu}_{r\phi} \kappa_{rr}) ; \quad M_{r\phi} = 0 ; \\ Q_{rz} &= k\tilde{G}_r h \gamma_{rz} ; \quad Q_{\phi z} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where

$$C = \frac{\tilde{E}_r h}{1 - \tilde{\nu}_{r\phi}^2}, \quad D = \frac{\tilde{E}_r h^3}{12(1 - \tilde{\nu}_{r\phi}^2)}. \quad (9)$$

The total elastic energy of the plate can be written as the sum of strain energies associated with bending, membrane and transverse shear forces

$$U = \frac{\pi D}{8\zeta^2} \left[26.38\gamma_{rz0}^2 \zeta^2 + 72w_0(\gamma_{rz0}\zeta + w_0) \right] + \frac{\pi \tilde{E}_r h}{8(1 - \tilde{\nu}_{r\phi}^2)} \frac{w_0^4}{\zeta^2} + \frac{5\pi \tilde{G}_r h}{32} \gamma_{rz0}^2 \zeta^2 \quad (10)$$

Upon neglecting effects of rotary inertia, the total kinetic energy of the system is given by

$$T = \pi\mu \left(0.214w_0^2 \dot{\zeta}^2 + 0.171w_0 \dot{w}_0 \zeta \dot{\zeta} + 0.0857\dot{w}_0^2 \zeta^2 \right) + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{w}_0^2 . \quad (11)$$

The Euler-Lagrange equations are now employed to solve for the time history of the degrees of freedom $w_0(t)$, $\zeta(t)$ and $\gamma_{rz0}(t)$. The Lagrangian function

$$L = T - U \quad (12)$$

is obtained by combining eqs. (10) and (11), and is used to derive the equations of motion of the system through the Euler-Lagrange equations

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{w}_0} \right) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial w_0} = 0 ; \quad \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\zeta}} \right) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial \zeta} = 0 ; \quad \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\gamma}_{rz0}} \right) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial \gamma_{rz0}} = 0. \quad (13)$$

Evaluating the derivatives in eq. (13) and writing the equations of motion (not explicitly given here) in non-dimensional terms, we find that the non-dimensional generalised coordinates

$$\bar{w}_0 = \frac{w_0}{R} ; \quad \bar{\zeta} = \frac{\zeta}{R} ; \quad \gamma_{rz0} \quad (14)$$

are functions of the non-dimensional time $\bar{t} = t\sqrt{\tilde{E}_r/\rho}/R$ and of the following set of non-dimensional parameters

$$\bar{h} = \frac{h}{R} ; \bar{M} = \frac{M}{\rho h R^2 \pi} ; \bar{v}_0 = v_0 \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\tilde{E}_r}} ; \bar{G} = \frac{\tilde{G}_r}{\tilde{E}_r} . \quad (15)$$

Here, \bar{w}_0 and $\bar{\zeta}$ represent the normalised centre deflection and flexural wave position, respectively, while the parameters \bar{h} , \bar{M} and \bar{v}_0 denote aspect ratio, mass ratio and non-dimensional impact velocity, respectively. The Phase 1 solutions are invalidated when the flexural wave reaches the plate boundary, $\bar{\zeta}(\bar{t})=1$, as different deformation modes are induced by the interaction with the plate's supports. Correspondingly we modify the shape functions for Phase 2 response, as detailed in the following section

2.2 Phase 2 response

We proceed to develop the equations for the Phase 2 response, accounting for the effects of the supports on the dynamic response of the plate. In a first approximation, we add two sinusoidal shape functions to the polynomial shape function considered for Phase 1

$$w(r,t) = w_0(t) \left[1 - \frac{3r^2}{R^2} + \frac{2r^3}{R^3} \right] + w_1(t) \sin\left(\frac{r\pi}{R}\right) + w_2(t) \cos\left(\frac{3r\pi}{2R}\right) \quad (16)$$

where $w_1(t)$ and $w_2(t)$ are the vertical displacement amplitudes corresponding to the first and second sinusoidal terms, respectively. It should be mentioned that only the first and last terms in eq. (27) contribute to the centre deflection, $w(r=0,t)$, therefore

$$w_{\text{tot}}(t) = w_0(t) + w_2(t) \quad (17)$$

is the total centre deflection in Phase 2 ($\bar{w} = w_{\text{tot}}/R$ in non-dimensional terms). Accordingly, the shear deflections in Phase 2 are modified to

$$\gamma_{rz}(r,t) = \gamma_{rz0}(t) \sin\left(\frac{r\pi}{R}\right) + \frac{\gamma_{rz1}(t)}{2} \sin\left(\frac{2r\pi}{R}\right) + \frac{\gamma_{rz2}(t)}{2} \sin\left(\frac{3r\pi}{R}\right), \quad (18)$$

where $\gamma_{rz1}(t)$ and $\gamma_{rz2}(t)$ are the shear deformation amplitudes associated to the first and second sinusoidal terms, respectively. The four additional DOFs introduced in Phase 2 can be normalised as

$$\bar{w}_1 = \frac{w_1}{R} ; \bar{w}_2 = \frac{w_2}{R} ; \gamma_{rz1} ; \gamma_{rz2}. \quad (19)$$

Again, the Euler-Lagrange equations (13) are employed to obtain the governing equations for the Phase 2 response, resulting in six non-dimensional equations of motion which can be solved numerically for the time histories $\bar{w}_0(\bar{t})$, $\bar{w}_1(\bar{t})$, $\bar{w}_2(\bar{t})$, $\gamma_{rz0}(\bar{t})$, $\gamma_{rz1}(\bar{t})$ and $\gamma_{rz2}(\bar{t})$. These equations are not explicitly given here for the sake of brevity.

3 COMPARISON OF ANALYTICAL AND FE PREDICTIONS

In this section, analytical predictions are compared to those obtained from detailed dynamic FE models with ABAQUS/Explicit, in order to validate our analytical model and to explore the sensitivity of the response to the governing non-dimensional parameters.

3.1 Deflection versus time histories

Analytical and FE predictions of centre deflection versus time are compared in this section in order to validate the analytical models derived in Section 2. In Fig. 2a, analytical and FE predictions of the normalised centre deflection $\bar{w}_0 = w_0/R$ are plotted as functions of the non-dimensional time,

$\bar{t} = t\sqrt{E/\rho}/R$, for the choice $\bar{h} = 0.1$, $\bar{M} = 0.6$ and $\bar{v}_0 = 0.04$. We also include in this figure predictions obtained from a reduced analytical model that ignores the excitation of the additional sinusoidal mode shapes during Phase 2 response. While the analytical and FE predictions are found in excellent agreement, the reduced model significantly under-predicts the deflection of the plate. Figure 2b presents the corresponding predictions of normalised flexural wave position, $\bar{\zeta} = \zeta/R$, as functions of \bar{t} . It can be seen from this figure that the analytical and FE predictions are again in good agreement, suggesting that the proposed analytical model adequately captures the details of the flexural wave propagation mechanism associated with the response of transversely impacted plates.

Figure 2: Comparison of analytical and FE predictions performed with $\bar{h} = 0.1$, $\bar{M} = 0.6$ and $\bar{v}_0 = 0.04$: (a) normalized center deflection, $\bar{w}_0 = w_0/R$, and (b) normalized flexural wave position, $\bar{\zeta} = \zeta/R$, as functions of non-dimensional time; t_1 denotes the Phase1/Phase2 transition.

3.2 Sensitivity of the predicted response to non-dimensional parameters

In this section, the analytical model is employed to examine the sensitivity of the deflection response to the governing non-dimensional parameters. For this study we considered cross-ply CFRP laminates comprising of unidirectional AS4/epoxy plies each of thickness $h_l = 0.125$ mm and density $\rho = 1580$ kgm⁻³. The elastic lamina properties were taken from [20] and the layups of the cross-ply laminates were chosen to be symmetric, $[0,90]_{ns}$. Analytical calculations and FE simulations were conducted on plates of radius $R = 50$ mm, and the laminate thickness h , the impact velocity v_0 and the projectile mass M were varied in order to construct a non-dimensional response map, as shown in Fig. 3. In this figure analytical predictions of the normalised peak deflection $\bar{w}_{\max} = w_{\max}/R$ are plotted as functions of the non-dimensional impact velocity \bar{v}_0 for the choice $\bar{M} = 0.1$, with contours of aspect ratio $\bar{h} = h/R$ included. Finite element predictions of \bar{w}_{\max} are also included for comparison. Both FE and analytical predictions are found in good agreement and show that the effect of increasing \bar{v}_0 is to monotonically increase \bar{w}_{\max} for any choice of \bar{h} , and that larger aspect ratios lead to smaller values of \bar{w}_{\max} . The good correlation between analytical and FE predictions gives us

confidence that our analytical model is able to accurately predict the peak deflections for a range of non-dimensional parameters.

We proceed to examine the sensitivity of plate deformation to variations of projectile dimensions, as quantified here by the normalised projectile radius, $\bar{R}_s = R_s/R$. Analytical calculations and FE simulations were performed with $\bar{G} = 0.4$, $\bar{M} = 0.6$ and $\bar{v}_0 = 0.022$, varying \bar{R}_s in the range of 0.04 to 0.5 and setting \bar{h} to either 0.05 or 0.1. Figure 3b reports the predicted sensitivity of the normalised peak centre deflection $\bar{w}_{\max} = \max(w_0/R)$ to variations of \bar{R}_s , for the two choices of \bar{h} ; analytical predictions corresponding to the chosen sets of non-dimensional parameters are included for comparison and show no sensitivity to \bar{R}_s , as expected. It can be seen from the FE predictions that variations in \bar{R}_s only play a minor role in the elastic deformation response, justifying the fact that in our analytical model the contact indentations was neglected.

Figure 3: (a) Analytical and FE predictions of the normalized peak deflection, $\bar{w}_{\max} = \max(w_0/R)$, for the case of cross-ply CFRP plates with $\bar{M} = 0.1$; contours of aspect ratio $\bar{h} = h/R$ are plotted for two different values; (b) analytical and FE predictions of \bar{w}_{\max} as functions of the normalized projectile radius $\bar{R}_s = R_s/R$ for $\bar{M} = 0.6$, $\bar{v}_0 = 0.022$ and two different values of $\bar{h} = h/R$.

3.3 Strain versus time histories

In this section we assess the accuracy of the strain predictions provided by our analytical model. To do this we compare analytical and FE predictions of the peak tensile strain induced in the laminate during the dynamic response.

Finite element simulations were performed on a CFRP plate of thickness $h = 2.5$ mm, radius $R = 50$ mm and lay-up $[0,90]_{5s}$ subject to impact at $v_0 = 86 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ by a ball projectile of mass $M = 3.1 \text{ g}$, giving $\bar{M} = 0.1$, $\bar{v}_0 = 0.016$ and $\bar{h} = 0.05$; the normalised projectile radius $\bar{R}_s = R_s/R$ was either 0.05, 0.1 or 0.2 in these calculations. Figure 4 presents the predicted time histories of radial fibre strain induced in the distal face of the laminate below the impact point, $\varepsilon_1(t)$; we also include in this figure the corresponding analytical predictions of $\varepsilon_1(t)$ which are insensitive to \bar{R}_s . The obtained predictions show that the strain rapidly rises and soon reaches a peak value, $\varepsilon_{1,\max}$, followed by a more moderate decay. The FE predictions in Fig. 4 show that the variations of the normalised plate radius, \bar{R}_s , have small effect on the strain response, $\varepsilon_1(t)$, for the range of \bar{R}_s considered here; the corresponding analytical prediction follows a similar trend and its peak value, $\varepsilon_{1,\max}$, is found in good correlation with the FE results. With the above loading conditions, the predicted $\varepsilon_{1,\max}$ values are higher than the quasi-static tensile ductility $\varepsilon_{1T}^* = 1.38\%$ shown in Fig. 4 as a reference.

Figure 4: Predicted time histories of the peak strain induced in a CFRP plate (stacking sequence $[0,90]_{5s}$, aspect ratio $\bar{h} = 0.05$) for the choice $\bar{M} = 0.1$; analytical and FE predictions are compared; the FE results are shown for three different projectile dimensions (quantified by R_0/R).

4 ONSET OF FAILURE

The validated analytical model is now used to explore the damage resistance of CFRP and GFRP laminates, as quantified by the critical velocity v_0^* at which the failure strain ε_{1T}^* is reached at the tensile face. Composite layups, average densities, tensile failure strains and effective elastic properties used for the CFRP and GFRP laminates are listed in Table 1.

lamina material	layup	ρ (kgm ⁻³)	\tilde{E}_r (GPa)	$\tilde{\nu}_{r\phi}$	\tilde{G}_r (GPa)	ε_{1T}^* (%)
CFRP	[0,90] _{ns}	1580	45.6	0.15	5.26	1.38
GFRP	[0,90] _{ns}	2030	24.4	0.26	5.81	2.8

Table 1: Stacking sequences, densities, failure strains and effective elastic properties of the GFRP and CFRP laminates considered here.

In Fig. 5a we present analytical predictions of the peak fibre strain $\varepsilon_{1,\max}$ induced in CFRP and GFRP plates with equal areal mass, $\mu = 3.95 \text{ kgm}^{-2}$, and layup, [0,90]_{ns}, as functions of v_0 for the choice $\bar{M} = 0.05$. The predictions show that the response of the GFRP plates is associated with larger values of $\varepsilon_{1,\max}$ compared to CFRP plates impacted at equal velocities; this can be justified by the lower equivalent stiffness \tilde{E}_r of the GFRP composite (see Table 1). However, taking into account the higher quasi-static ductility of the GFRP laminate, $\varepsilon_{1T}^* = 2.8\%$ (Table 1), it follows that the critical velocity v_0^* of the GFRP laminates are approximately 30% higher than those predicted for the stiffer (and more brittle) CFRP plates ($\varepsilon_{1T}^* = 1.38\%$, see Table 1). This allows concluding that typical GFRP composites may outperform CFRP laminates in terms of damage resistance.

We now employ the analytical model to determine damage-resistant plate designs and construct design charts in the $\bar{h} - \bar{M}$ - space, for the practical ranges $0.01 \leq \bar{M} \leq 1$ and $0.02 \leq \bar{h} \leq 0.14$. Figure 5b presents such a map for the case of GFRP cross-ply laminates (see Table 1). We include in Fig. 5b contours of non-dimensional critical impact velocity, \bar{v}_0^* , defined as the velocity at which the maximum tensile strain in the laminate reaches the failure strain of the material, $\varepsilon_{1,\max} = \varepsilon_{1T}^* = 2.8\%$ (Table 1). Note that the area left to each \bar{v}_0^* - contour represents the design space $\{\bar{h}, \bar{M}\}$ in which the laminate can safely withstand ballistic impact without fibre damage, i.e. $\varepsilon_{1,\max} < \varepsilon_{1T}^*$.

Figure 5: (a) Analytical predictions of peak tensile strain for the case $\bar{M} = 0.05$ as a function of impact velocity v_0 for CFRP and GFRP plates with equal areal mass, $\mu = 3.95 \text{ kgm}^{-2}$, and layup, $[0,90]_{ns}$; the crosses indicate points of incipient failure. (b) Design chart in the $\bar{M} - \bar{h}$ space for the case of cross-ply GFRP laminates with contours of non-dimensional impact velocity, $\bar{v}_0^* = v_0^* \sqrt{\rho / \tilde{E}_r}$, at the onset of tensile failure, $\varepsilon_{1,\max} = \varepsilon_{1T}^* = 2.8\%$.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We developed and validated a physically based model for predicting the dynamic deformation of fully clamped, circular elastic composite plates subject to impact by a rigid projectile. The mathematical framework is based on first-order shear deformation theory of plates and takes into account large deformation, propagation of flexural waves as well as higher-order vibrational modes emerging in the boundary-controlled phase of the response; local indentation at the impact point as well as ply damage and failure are not explicitly modelled. The constitutive response of the composite was linear elastic with effective stiffness deduced from the stiffness matrix of the laminate; the mathematical formulation of plate deflection was based on axisymmetric shape functions assumed a priori. This approach yields a set of nonlinear ODEs which can be solved using common numerical integration methods.

The dynamic response was found to be governed by only four non-dimensional parameters: aspect ratio, mass ratio, non-dimensional impact velocity and transverse shear stiffness. The analytical models were validated by comparing the predicted centre deflections and peak strains to those of detailed dynamic FE simulations, and a good correlation was found for a wide range of parameters. It was shown that neglecting additional vibrational modes during the boundary-controlled phase of the response can lead to large inaccuracies in the predictions. In addition, detailed FE simulations showed that the deflection response of elastic plates is only mildly sensitive to the projectile radius.

The sensitivity of peak tensile strain to variations of the projectile velocity was examined for two types of composites, (i) carbon-fibre/epoxy (CFRP) and (ii) glass-fibre/epoxy (GFRP) laminates. The critical velocities for inception of tensile failure were found, as expected, below the measured limit velocities for full penetration. It was shown that the GFRP plates can sustain higher impact velocities at the inception of failure compared to plates made from CFRP of equal mass, concluding that GFRP composites outperform stiffer and more brittle CFRP laminates in terms of impact damage resilience.

Finally, the analytical models were used to construct design maps for GFRP laminates in order to aid the selection of damage-resistant plate geometries.

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